

conditions, the three varieties yielded similarly. The participating farmers were generally satisfied with the performance of the new varieties. OHV has undertaken seed multiplication of all three varieties. □

Ranbir Basmati — an early-maturing aromatic rice

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The quality basmati rices of India and Pakistan, characterized by late maturity, are difficult to fit into multiple farming systems, and are grown on limited hectareage. Development of early-maturing basmati types would help bring larger areas under superfine rices.

In 1982, we isolated an early-maturing, slightly dwarf plant from farmers' fields. The strain, Ranbir Basmati, was evaluated against Basmati 370 for 2 yr at RARS, and in farmers' fields for performance, stability, and adaptability. Ranbir Basmati duration is 115-120 d from sowing to maturity, 30-35 d shorter than that of Basmati 370, with comparable yields. Yield per day of Ranbir Basmati was 20-25% higher. Grain quality equaled or surpassed that of Basmati 370 (see table). □

Comparative qualities of Ranbir Basmati and Basmati 370.

Character	Ranbir Basmati	Basmati 370
Plant height (cm)	155	170
Duration (d)	115	150
Threshability	Easy	Easy
Grain length (mm)	7.2	7.1
Grain breadth (mm)	1.8	1.9
Length/breadth ratio	3.9	3.8
Chalkiness	5	9
1,000-grain wt (g)	22.8	21.5
Amylose content (%)	24.0	21.3
Gelatinization temperature ^a	I/L	H/I
Average proportional elongation ratio	2.05	2.03
Protein content (%)	7.7	7.0
Aroma	Strong	Strong
Cooking quality	Good	Good
Eating quality	Good	Good

^a L = low, H = high, I = intermediate.

RAU4045-10, a new variety for rainfed areas

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RAU4045-10 (IET7978), a semidwarf variety derived from Finegora/ IET2832, is moderately resistant to blast and averages 70 d to 50% flowering. Mean yield over 4 yr of experimental trials was 3.6 t/ha, significantly higher than that of check varieties Akashi (2.3 t/ha) and Brown gora (2.1 t/ha).

IET7978 was tested for 3 yr in All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement

Project (AICRIP) experiments. In the 1984 Preliminary Varietal Trial 1 (PVT-1), it yielded 5.5 t/ha at Hyderabad. In the 1985 Uniform Varietal Trial in 15 locations all over India, it yielded an average 2.6 t/ha and took 74 d to flowering under direct seeded rainfed conditions (Table 1) and 3.7 t/ha under direct seeded irrigated conditions. It ranked third in transplanted conditions in 16 locations.

In 1986, IET7978 was the top yielder (3 t/ha) over all locations (Table 2). It significantly outyielded national as well as local checks under rainfed conditions in Bihar and Orissa and has been recommended for rainfed fields in Bihar and Orissa. □

Table 1. Performance of RAU4045-10 in station trials at Birsa Agricultural University, Kanke, Ranchi, India.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)				
	1983	1984	1985	1986	Mean
RAU4045-10 (IET7978)	4.2	3.8	3.0	3.4	3.6
Akashi	2.5	2.4	2.1	2.4	2.3
Brown gora	1.9	2.0	2.2	2.3	2.1
LSD (0.05)	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.4

Table 2. Performance of RAU4045-10 in All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project trials during 1986.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)								
	Zone III		Zone 5		Mean	Zone 8		Transplanting condition	
	Assam	Assam and Tripura	Kanke Bihar	Faizabad (U.P.)		Himachal Pradesh	Tamil Nadu	Delhi	Rajasthan
RAU4045-10	2.6	3.1	4.1	4.1	3.1	3.7	5.0	5.9	3.0
Akashi	2.1	3.0	3.2	4.4	2.9	2.1	4.0	3.4	2.4
Cauvery	1.4	2.2	2.4	3.2	2.3	1.8	4.5	4.8	2.9
Local checks	—	—	2.2	3.6	—	2.8	4.7	—	—
				(N22)		(HPU741)	(IR50)		

CN705-18 — a promising rice variety for deepwater rice areas

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Based on overall performance in 1985-87 national trials, CN705-18 (IET9065 =

Mahsuril CN643) is a promising variety for deepwater rice areas (water accumulates up to 1 m during the wet season) in West Bengal, Bihar, Andhra Pradesh, and Assam.

Photoperiod-sensitive CN705-18 flowered 28-30 Oct in West Bengal. Depending on water depth, it attained 175-210 cm height, with 10-12 tillers/hill. It has very good submergence

Performance of CN705-18 in multilocal trials in India, 1985-87.^a

Site ^b	Grain yield ^c (t/ha)		Max water depth (cm)
	CN705-18	Local check	
<i>Preliminary Variety Trial 5, 1985</i>			
Bhubaneswar	2.1*	1.0 (Khajuniachar)	na
CRRRI	3.6*	1.2 (CR1030)	40
Patna	2.5	2.7 (Janki)	na
Chinsurah	3.3*	1.8 (NC492)	55
<i>Uniform Variety Trial 5, 1986</i>			
Chinsurah	3.3*	1.2 (TCA212)	110
Malda	3.6	3.2 (CN540)	62
Pusa	1.2	1.8 (TCA214)	85
Ranital	2.2	1.7 (CR1030)	65
<i>Physiology screening</i>			
Cuttack	4.7*	3.4 (CR1018)	50
Patna	3.2*	2.2 (Janki)	50
<i>Uniform Variety Trial 5, 1987</i>			
CRRRI	3.5*	1.9 (na)	75
Bhubaneswar	2.1	2.0 (Rambha)	50
North Lakhimpur	2.9	2.9 (Panikekau)	108
Chinsurah	3.4	2.9 (NC492)	85
Pulla	2.0*	1.1 (CN540)	75
<i>Physiology screening</i>			
Chinsurah	4.0	4.0 (Jogen)	65
Maruteru	2.0*	0.7 (Marutan)	50
Mean (17 sites)	2.9	2.1	

^ana = data not available. ^bCRRRI = Central Rice Research Institute. ^c* = significant at the 5% level of probability.

tolerance, elongation ability, kneeing ability, and drought tolerance at the early vegetative stage. Panicles are about 24 cm long with good exertion and about 215 grains/panicle. Grain is medium and bold (length-5.9 mm, breadth-2.9 mm, L/B 2.0), 1,000-grain weight is 27.3 g. It has a yellow-colored hull at maturity, red kernel, and strong (3 mo) seed dormancy.

On average, CN705-18 outyielded check varieties (2.9 t/ha to 2.1 t/ha) over 17 sites (see table), with an overall yield increase of 38%. CN705-18 yield was significantly higher than check at 9 sites, superior at 4, equal at 2, and lower at 2. Yield varied from 4.7 to 1.2 t/ha. This variation under similar water depths over sites reflects the role of time, duration, and intensity of water stagnation in determining variety adaptability.

CN705-18 has been recommended for large-scale demonstration trials in farmers' fields. □

SiPi 692033: a promising rainfed lowland rice variety

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SiPi 692033 (introduced from Taiwan), seven FAROX rice lines (Table 1), and FARO 27 (a widely cultivated rice variety) were evaluated at six sites across the country in 1986. Sites 1, 2, and 3 lie within the rain forest and sites 4, 5, and 6 lie in the Sudan savanna vegetational zones.

All cultural operations except weed control were common to all locations. Grain yield (14% moisture) was taken from the middle 6 m² of each test plot.

SiPi 692033 was the highest yielder overall and at five sites. Its yield advantage ranged from 18% over FAROX 228-3-1-1 to 65% over FAROX 239-2-1-1.

In general, grain yields were higher at the Sudan savanna sites with low annual rainfall (<1,000 mm) than at the rain forest sites with high annual rainfall

Table 1. Yield of rice lines and varieties in multilocation trials in Nigeria, 1986.^a

Line or variety	Parentage	Grain yield (t/ha)						Mean
		1	2	3	4	5	6	
FAROX 228-3-1-1	FARO 15/IR28	1.1	5.4	4.4	6.1	8.2	8.2	5.6
FAROX 228-4-1-1	FARO 15/IR28	1.3	5.7	5.0	5.1	7.8	7.1	5.3
FAROX 239-3-3-2	IR28/FARO 12	1.0	4.8	6.4	6.5	5.7	7.6	5.3
FAROX 233-7-1-2	FARO 12/IR28	1.3	3.9	4.5	5.8	4.6	6.9	4.5
FAROX 239-2-1-1	IR28/FARO 12	1.0	3.3	3.6	5.5	4.1	6.4	4.0
FAROX 233-1-1-1	FARO 12/IR28	1.1	5.5	5.9	5.7	5.2	7.0	5.1
FAROX 234-3-1-1	FARO 12/TOS103	1.5	4.5	5.7	7.0	6.0	6.8	5.3
SiPi 692033	SiPi 661044/ SiPi 651020	1.5	5.9	5.9	8.9	8.3	8.8	6.6
FARO 27 (check)	-	1.3	5.2	5.0	6.9	3.6	7.2	4.9
Mean		1.2	4.9	5.2	6.4	5.9	7.3	

^aLocations: 1 = Ogoja, 2 = Ibadan, 3 = Bende, 4 = Wurno, 5 = Birnin-Kebbi, 6 = Kadawa.

Table 2. Agronomic characteristics of rice lines and varieties.^a Nigeria, 1986.

Line or variety	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Maturity (d)	Grain type ^b
FAROX 228-3-1-1	110	335	117	MB
FAROX 228-4-1-1	106	311	114	MB
FAROX 239-3-3-2	109	362	114	MB
FAROX 233-7-1-2	97	356	110	LS
FAROX 239-2-1-1	78	362	108	LS
FAROX 233-1-1-1	108	379	115	LS
FAROX 234-3-1-1	94	371	119	LS
SiPi 692033	106	339	122	LS
FARO 27 (check)	95	355	120	MB

^a Mean of 6 sites. ^b LS = long slender, MB = medium bold.